

Article

Process Simulation of a Microfluidic Micromixer for Pharmaceutical Production of DNA-Lipid Nanoparticles

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Abstract

Background/Objectives: The question addressed in the current work is to develop a simulation of a pharmaceutical process (DNA encapsulation within lipid nanoparticles using a microfluidic micromixer) which will be of utility to the end users (laboratory-scale formulation development). The simulation and the microfluidic approach also address sustainability issues, such as reducing the environmental impact of the process itself, and reducing the need for physical testing. The paper details the implementation and validation, taking into account key performance indicators and control parameters. **Methods:** The main method applied for simulation development is a novel multi-agent approach to incorporate stochastic probabilistic behavior, combined with theoretical definitions from the process experts and relevant literature, and data/results from laboratory-scale experiments with different parameter configurations. **Results:** The simulation was implemented as a representation of the real physical process, reproducing the relationships between process parameters (flow rates) and experimental key performance indicators (capsule diameter, poly dispersion index, encapsulation efficiency). The simulation results demonstrated a general agreement with the empirical results and provided useful predictive insights for the laboratory experiments. **Conclusions:** The simulation has potential as a support tool for laboratory experiments to reduce physical testing and indicate the most promising configurations on which to focus, with potential savings in time, resources and other costs.

Keywords: process simulation; multi-agents; microfluidics; micromixer; encapsulation; lipid nanoparticles; sustainability; calibration; optimization

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1. Introduction

Process simulation can be a valuable tool as support for process calibration and experimentation. In the following work, a simulation is built for a microfluidic micromixer apparatus for DNA-lipid nanoparticle encapsulation to help identify the most promising control parameter configurations for optimal encapsulation efficiency and capsule size and quality. The literature reports different levels of success in finding optimum operability at laboratory scale. In the current work, customized software is developed from scratch using

a multi-agent AI programming approach, which differentiates from proprietary software tools such as Dynochem and Simulink. For a complex simulation such as the micromixer DNA-lipid encapsulator, a key difference is that the multi-agent system approach can be considered 'bottom-up' and is able to model local micro-environments/fluctuations within the micromixer. On the other hand, an application such as DynoChem relies on the definition of deterministic differential equations and can be considered a 'top-down' approach. Furthermore, the deterministic model tends to take the average of groups of values; for example, capsule size and/or concentration is averaged for a series of discrete zones. On the other hand, a multi-agent simulation captures the stochastic formation of 'outlier' particles; for example, if the average capsule size is 60 nm, there will be a small number of capsules with a capsule size over 130 nm.

In terms of the sustainability of the physical process, a mixing approach (microfluidics) has a smaller environmental footprint than other approaches used in the industry, and in terms of the simulation, it reduces the need for physical testing of different flow rates in order to find an optimum configuration.

Firstly, the main concepts covered in the work are described, followed by approaches for process simulation (Section 1.1), the pharmaceutical process to be simulated (Section 1.2), sustainability (Section 1.3) and the main aim and paper organization (Section 1.4).

1.1. Approaches for Process Simulation in the Context of the Work

In the current work, a simulation is developed of the physical process of DNA encapsulation with lipids using a micromixer apparatus, incorporating theoretical definitions (such as Bernoulli equations governing fluid dynamics, Reynolds and Dean equations for measuring turbulence, kinetic interactions governing particle movement, electrostatic force, probability distributions, etc.) and artificial intelligence/statistical techniques (multi-agent system, advanced data analytics). Its intention is to be used as support for laboratory-scale experiments to quickly test candidate configurations, identifying the most promising and excluding the least promising, before going on to the physical experiments. The digital simulation consists of a to-scale definition of the microfluidic micromixer apparatus and the components of the DNA encapsulation process (DNA and lipids). The process is governed by two main variables: TFR (total flow rate) and FRR (flow rate ratio).

In terms of related work, in [1], the authors considered turbulent flows, using Lagrangian modeling applied to scalar micromixing, and incorporated the Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) equations. In the field of microfluidics, van Ballegoie et al. [2] studied the use of a system to synthesize protein nanoparticles, in which factors were evaluated which affected KPIs such as size, homogeneity and stability.

In terms of pharma applications, some simulations have been developed for non-biological complex drugs manufacturing [3], solidified nanosuspensions [4], and tabletting [5]; however, to the best of our knowledge, none have been developed for the application described in this paper.

A multi-agent system [6] approach using the Repast Symphony software development tool [7] was chosen for implementing the process simulation back-end (fluid dynamics, particle kinetics and particle interaction dynamics), as well as the front-end control panel and real-time visualization of the process simulation. The multi-agent system allows for programming of the individual behavior of each particle, allowing for the combination of limited stochastic behavior with predefined formulas and empirical rules.

As well as the theoretical aspects (equations, formulas and principles which govern the system being simulated), the available empirical data generated from testing at the Reig Jofre Laboratories was analyzed and modeled to provide control rules for the digital twin. As a first step, basic statistical analysis such as PCA and regression models were

applied, followed by the use of a clustering technique combined with a decision tree induction algorithm. This provided additional supporting rules which associate the control parameters with the key KPI being modeled (capsule diameter) [8–10].

In silico software simulation, also referred to as a “digital twin”, has the objective, given the same inputs, to produce the same outcomes as closely as possible to the physical process. Such a simulation can be offline (e.g., for testing scenarios before building/testing a physical version) or online (e.g., for real-time control and monitoring of the physical process). Hybrid versions exist (offline/online), such as for finding the optimum control set points for a given set of conditions before running the physical process.

Example process simulations using multi-agent system software include [11] in which a simulation was developed of in vitro T-cell behavior for immunologic alternatives to cancer treatment, and [12] in which a simulation was built for predicting the biodegradation of bioplastics. Example process simulations using system dynamics modeling include [13] in which Estivill et al. developed a simulation for hyperinflammation in COVID-19 patients. In terms of data-driven simulations, Barriga et al. [14] developed a simulation of a fluid bed dryer apparatus to optimize the drying time of product material in pharmaceutical manufacturing.

1.2. Description of the Pharmaceutical Process to Be Simulated

The DNA encapsulation process in DNA–lipid nanoparticle (DNA-LNP) encapsulation is a rapid, diffusion-limited self-assembly process occurring when an ethanolic solution of lipids (typically an ionizable amine lipid, helper phospholipid such as DSPC, cholesterol, and a PEG-lipid) is mixed with an aqueous acidic buffer containing DNA. Upon mixing, ethanol dilution and protonation of the ionizable lipid drive electrostatic complexation with the polyanionic DNA, and concomitant nucleation/growth of nanoscale lipid assemblies that mature into LNPs (commonly ~60–120 nm) with DNA sequestered in the particle core [15–18]. Process performance is governed by: (a) Flow parameters, primarily the total flow rate (TFR), which sets the characteristic mixing time (thus affecting nucleation rate, size, and polydispersity), and the flow rate ratio (FRR) (aqueous:organic), which establishes ethanol dilution kinetics and local pH/ionic micro-environments. Together, these strongly influence particle size distribution, encapsulation efficiency, and morphology [16,17,19–21]. (b) Formulation parameters, including the N/P (amine:phosphate) ratio, total lipid concentration, buffer composition/molarity and pH, and lipid composition/structure, all of which modulate complexation, phase behavior, and final LNP architecture [15,18,20,21]. Following mixing, neutralization/buffer-exchange (e.g., into physiological buffers) stabilizes particles and sets their surface charge near neutrality, which is conducive to biocompatibility and in vivo performance [15,18,20,22].

1.3. Sustainability

In this work, sustainability is addressed from two key viewpoints:

- (i) The simulation has potential as a support tool for laboratory experiments to reduce physical testing and indicate the most promising configurations on which to focus, with potential savings in time, resource usage and waste. Specifically, the simulation tests different flow rates in order to find a combination which minimizes resource input while maximizing the KPIs (capsule size and encapsulation efficiency).
- (ii) The microfluidic micromixer apparatus for DNA-lipid nanoparticle encapsulation has greater sustainability and a smaller environmental footprint compared to other approaches for DNA-LNP production.

Microfluidic mixing has recently become a current industry standard for DNA-LNP production. However, several alternative approaches exist, which are generally considered less sustainable as they fail to meet several “green chemistry” goals, mainly due to higher waste, energy intensity, and hazardous solvent requirements. These approaches

are listed as follows. (i) Impinging jet mixing (IJM)—instead of mixing in microchannels (as in microfluidics), two high-pressure jets (lipids in ethanol vs. DNA in buffer) collide at high velocity in a small T-junction or chamber, using turbulent kinetic energy to force the two phases together. It has worse sustainability due to (a) higher reagent waste due to turbulence and (b) higher energy consumption as it requires high pressure operation. (ii) Thin-film hydration (the Bangham method)—a traditional method in which lipids are dissolved in a solvent and dried onto a flask to form a film. A DNA buffer is added, and the flask is shaken. It has worse sustainability due to (a) hazardous solvents: chloroform or dichloromethane (instead of ethanol in microfluidics) to get the lipids to form a proper film, and (b) low efficiency: the encapsulation efficiency is often as low as 30–50%. (iii) High-pressure homogenization (HPH)—a coarse mixture of lipids and DNA is repeatedly forced through a narrow valve at extreme pressures (up to 2000 bar) in which mechanical shear and cavitation break the particles down to size. It has worse sustainability due to (a) thermal waste: a large amount of heat is generated and intensive cooling systems are required, and (b) cleaning waste: the cleaning of the chambers requires large amounts of purified water and detergents, whereas microfluidics use small, recyclable, or easily flushed chips. (iv) Solvent evaporation (emulsification)—creates a “water-in-oil-in-water” emulsion and then evaporates the oil phase to leave the nanoparticles behind. An organic solvent is used as a bridge to hold the lipids before being slowly removed by a vacuum or heat. This process is less sustainable given (a) air emissions: the evaporated solvents can be released into the atmosphere, and (b) slow cycle times: the process can take hours or days, leading to a high “time-to-dose” ratio.

In the current study, a formal life cycle assessment (LCA) or a complete mass/energy inventory was not performed. However, it is proposed that one of the practical advantages of the digital twin framework is the reduction in the number of experimental iterations required during process optimization. This can reasonably be expected to decrease solvent consumption, raw material use, and laboratory-generated waste, while also reducing instrument operating time.

1.4. Main Aim and Paper Organization

The main aim of the work is to build a useful simulation of a microfluidic micromixer apparatus for DNA encapsulation in lipid nanoparticles, which can be calibrated using the key control parameters of TFR and FRR, and whose result can be quantifiably measured and compared with the real empirical process, using encapsulation efficiency and capsule diameter as outcomes. The key conclusions are that a useful simulation of this process can be developed, which provides a beneficial tool to help the laboratory experimental stage in finding the most promising configurations and discounting the least viable ones.

The paper is organized as follows: in Section 2, the materials and methods are described with particular detail into the digital twin development and background; in Section 3, the simulation results are presented and compared with the corresponding real empirical results data; in Section 4, there is a discussion regarding the hypothesis validation and what has been achieved with respect to the initial objectives, as well as potential future work. Finally, the conclusion provides a hindsight overview, and Supplementary Material is indicated (video, runtime, data) for the research community.

2. Materials and Methods

The following section provides details of the materials and methods used with a view to help fellow researchers replicate and build on the published results. Access to Supplementary Materials (video, data, executable application) is indicated in the corresponding section at the end of the paper. Firstly, Sections 2.1 and 2.2 describe the apparatus

and the physical process, the NxGen™ micromixer (Precision NanoSystems, Vancouver, BC, Canada) and the formulation and characterization of DNA–lipid nanoparticles, respectively. Next, Sections 2.3 and 2.4 describe the digital representation of the micromixer and the information technology configuration details, with reference to the multi-agent architecture. Finally, Section 2.5 details the key scientific concepts which are programmed in the simulation: fluid dynamics, electrostatic forces, Brownian motion, turbulence control and key performance indicators (capsule size and encapsulation efficiency).

2.1. NxGen Micromixer Apparatus (Ignite Platform)

Microfluidic micromixers operate in the laminar regime, where convective stretching and interface striation, rather than turbulence, accelerate molecular diffusion between an organic lipid stream and an aqueous nucleic-acid stream. Architectures such as hydrodynamic flow-focusing and passive chaotic-advection designs (e.g., staggered herringbone mixers, SHM or toroidal mixers, TrM) reduce characteristic mixing length/time by inducing secondary transverse flows while maintaining low Reynolds numbers; performance is commonly rationalized via the resulting ethanol–buffer dilution trajectory that governs LNP nucleation and growth [23–26].

The design variables encoded in the cartridge and flow path—channel cross-section and length, internal microfeatures, surface/material—tune the local mixing time and ethanol dilution kinetics, thereby selecting the nucleation/assembly pathway and ultimately particle size distribution and polydispersity [23–25].

Experiments were performed on a NanoAssemblr™ Ignite system (Cytiva (Marlborough, MA, USA)/Precision Nanosystems) (Figure 1) equipped with single-use NxGen™ microfluidic cartridges configured with two inlets (aqueous and organic), operated according to the manufacturer’s instructions. The platform allows precise control of the total flow rate (TFR, sum of inlet volumetric flow rates) and of the flow-rate ratio (FRR, aqueous:organic), while maintaining laminar, reproducible mixing within the NxGen cartridge [25,26]. The system supports bench-scale formulation at up to 20 mL total volume and 20 mL·min^{−1} flow rate.

Figure 1. NxGen micromixer (Ignite Platform).

2.2. Formulation and Characterization of DNA–Lipid Nanoparticles

Lipid nanoparticles were formulated using the same lipid components and molar ratio reported for the Pfizer–BioNTech COVID-19 vaccine (Comirnaty[®]): the ionizable lipid ALC-0315, DSPC, cholesterol, and the PEGylated lipid ALC-0159 at 46.3:9.4:42.7:1.6 (mol%). Lipid stocks were prepared in anhydrous ethanol to match this composition class. The nucleic acid cargo was an oligonucleotide sequence, dissolved in citrate buffer; the oligonucleotide sequence was synthesized by GenScript (HPLC-purified; length 52 nt; %G/C 42.3; %A/T 57.7), reconstituted at 62 ng· μL^{-1} , and stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ according to the manufacturer's recommendations. Formulations were produced by loading the aqueous oligonucleotide solution and the lipid–ethanol solution into the respective inlets and initiating simultaneous flow; to ensure steady-state collection, 0.30 mL were discarded at the start of each run before product collection because the system had not yet reached the selected TFR conditions and the outflow could therefore be non-representative, making it impossible to guarantee the reproducible formation of properly assembled nanoparticles; an additional 0.05 mL was discarded at the end of the formulation for the same reason. Note that the simulation evaluates the process under idealized steady operating conditions from the beginning of the run and therefore does not reproduce the initial and final transient fractions that are excluded experimentally.

The nitrogen-to-phosphate ratio (N/P) was fixed at 5.5 for all experiments. TFR and FRR (aqueous:organic) were varied across five conditions: {FRR = 4.5, TFR = 8 mL·min⁻¹}, {FRR = 8.5825, TFR = 8 mL·min⁻¹}, {FRR = 0.4175, TFR = 8 mL·min⁻¹}, {FRR = 4.5, TFR = 11.266 mL·min⁻¹}, and {FRR = 4.5, TFR = 4.734 mL·min⁻¹}. Immediately after formulation, dispersions were diluted 1:40 (*v/v*) in PBS and reconcentrated by centrifugal ultrafiltration to the original batch volume using Amicon[®] Ultra devices (15 mL capacity, regenerated cellulose membrane, MWCO 50 kDa; Merck (Rahway, NJ, USA)) to normalize ethanol content and buffer conditions. Hydrodynamic size (*Z*-average) and polydispersity index (PDI) were measured by dynamic light scattering (DLS) at 25 °C using cumulants analysis on samples diluted 1:20 in PBS to the instrument's recommended count rate.

2.3. Digital Representation of the Micromixer Apparatus

Initially, the schema depicted in Figure 2 [26] was defined to-scale in the simulation 2D solution space of the Repast Symphony multi-agent software (which is then shown dynamically on the user front-end screen—see Section 3). For example, the width of the internal tube was considered as 15 units (see Figure 2). The DNA, lipid and capsule sizes were limited by the resolution of the multi-agent system 2D grid definition which is displayed on the screen. Hence, 1 grid square was considered as the minimum resolution for particle size and the dimension units for the micromixer were considered as 1 grid square = 1 unit, so the internal tube was defined as 150 grid squares in diameter. This grid resolution was found to be sufficient in order to give an approximation of the particle kinetics and fluid dynamics behavior of the system. The optimum dimensions of the 2D solution space for the *in silico* simulation were defined as 130 by 400 (grid squares). These values were assigned after testing greater and smaller dimensionalities and choosing the maximum values which allowed the software to run in a commodity hardware computer, while showing correct execution of the simulation. A detailed study of dimensionality testing does not form part of the current work; however, it was found that lower dimensionalities (e.g., 36 by 111, 50 by 154) with a constant ratio of 1:3.08 (to fit the to-scale micromixer structure) showed inferior performance as the relatively smaller microchannel width (along which the particles flow) was not sufficient to allow the particle dynamics to perform well. Another consideration is the definition of the micromixer walls, which require sufficient granularity as a surface for particle collisions. On reaching 100 by 308, a good performance was found, whereas

150×462 processed very slowly and resulted in intermittent blocking of the computer run. Hence, 130×400 was found to be optimum on the available hardware, as a tradeoff between runtime computer performance and quality of simulation. For this optimum dimensionality, the microchannel mixer width was set proportionally at 15.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the toroidal micromixer [26].

The schematic definition of the micromixer given in Figure 2 [26] corresponds to the specific model of lab scale micromixer used by Reig Jofre for the experiments described in the paper. The characteristic channel dimension of the toroidal micromixer shown in Figure 2 is approximately $150 \mu\text{m}$.

2.4. Information Technology Configuration Details and Software Development Environment

Repast Symphony 2.8 [7] with Java 11 was used for the multi-agent software development. Figure 3 shows the overall schema of the definition of the agents for the simulation model. On the lower right are the overall coordinator and scheduler which control the main individual agents in the center, which are the nucleic acid, lipids and encapsulates. The barrier agent is a static agent which forms the tubular structure of the micromixer. Auxiliary agent types (middle right) control the spatial movement and positioning, and the generation, extraction and counting/statistics (lower left). The key scientific concepts (fluid dynamics, electrostatic forces, etc.) described in Section 2.5 were programmed in the main scheduler, the individual particle agents (lipid, nucleic acid, etc.), spatial controller and generator, extractor and barrier.

To develop the simulation, a machine learning pipeline was defined to perform data analytics to help define an AI multi-agent framework process simulation. Integrating unsupervised clustering with supervised decision trees facilitates data modeling for scenarios where pre-existing data labels are either unavailable, difficult to generate, or statistically unreliable.

The K-means [27] algorithm is a key unsupervised machine learning technique utilized to partition datasets into discrete clusters based on the statistical similarity of individual observations. The algorithm establishes a predetermined number of centroids and iteratively assigns data points to their nearest cluster center. This process continues in an iterative cycle until a convergence threshold is met, typically defined by the simultaneous minimization of intra-cluster variance and the maximization of inter-cluster separation. In the present work, clustering serves a dual function: it provides intrinsic analytical utility and generates the predictive targets (cluster IDs) required for the subsequent decision tree algorithm. This methodological integration is particularly applicable when an a priori labeling of cases is

unavailable, which is the situation for the data being processed [28]. Cluster validation was executed through a dual-objective approach incorporating the elbow (or knee) heuristic together with entropy-based considerations. The elbow method facilitates the identification of the optimal cluster count (k) by evaluating the within-cluster sum of squares (WCSS) as a function of ' k ', using the `model.inertia_` attribute of the Python V3.9 `KneeLocator` function.

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of Repast Symphony V2.8 multi-agent software implementation.

The decision tree algorithm used is an optimized version of the classification and regression trees (CART) algorithm [28], widely used for the classification of multi-dimensional variables [10,29]. The algorithm produces a hierarchical model characterized by a series of nodes and branches, where each non-terminal node encapsulates a decision rule derived from optimized thresholds for specific attributes deemed representative of the target output(s). The decision tree was implemented using the `DecisionTreeClassifier` Python (V3.9) function from the `scikit-learn` library, which employs splitting heuristics via the criterion parameter, including 'Gini' (Gini impurity) and 'entropy' (information gain). Model performance was quantified using the `accuracy_score` metric, representing the ratio of correct label predictions to the total observations within the test set. To ensure robustness, the training phase was executed over five iterations, with the model demonstrating the highest predictive accuracy retained for final deployment. Consequently, the integration of clustering and decision tree methodologies enables the identification of parameter ranges and control logic for the TFR and FRR configurations, helping to define the empirical foundation for process simulation calibration.

The software working principles applied during software design and development included the AGILE/SCRUM methodology. The objective of these principles is to create software that is reliable, maintainable, scalable, and efficient. They allow the correct definition of user requirements and their development and implementation in the system, thus ensuring that the final system meets user needs while facilitating future updating and adaptations. Unitary internal (technical) testing is first performed by the programming team, which is followed by end user evaluation (external) and feedback, which is completed in an iterative manner until all the requirements are met.

2.5. Key Concepts of Simulation

The following describes the key concepts implemented in the simulation to govern the process: fluid dynamics and Bernoulli principle (Section 2.5.1), electrostatic forces between particles (Section 2.5.2), Brownian motion of particles (Section 2.5.3), turbulence control (Section 2.5.4) and key performance indicators (Section 2.5.5).

It is noted that in microfluidics, wall resistance and wall shear stress can be important factors. In the present work, these concepts have been simplified to build the simulation, assuming steady flow rate and uniform geometry. Furthermore, kinetic and Brownian particle dynamics are fully represented, so particle-wall interaction is built into the model. This allows differentiation from a purely equation-based system dynamics model.

2.5.1. Fluid Dynamics—Bernoulli Principle

The Bernoulli equation represents the inverse relationship between the speed at which a fluid is flowing and the pressure it is subject to. In the digital twin simulation, to calculate the speed at which particles move, Bernoulli's equation is used to relate pressure, density, and speed, assuming there is no gravitational acceleration. The dimensions of the micromixer are exactly scaled to size to represent the tube volumes, length, diameters, etc. Specific equations determine the flow on the unification or splitting of the tubes (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Bernoulli's principle (flow continuity) applied to different segments of the micromixer apparatus.

2.5.2. Electrostatic Forces Between Charged Particles

The electrostatic force between two charged particles is governed by an inverse square law, meaning the force is inversely proportional to the square of the distance between them.

In the digital twin simulation, the electrostatic force and inverse square law are implemented as the attractor between the DNA and the lipids (Figure 5). A probability value has been incorporated so that the attraction between a DNA and/or capsule depends on the number of DNA and lipids in the capsule. Once a capsule acquires three DNA and 15 lipids (the optimum as specified by the physical process), the attraction probability reduces proportionately so there is less chance of new DNA and lipids adhering to the

capsule. Also, the process has been simplified so that the hydrophilic and hydrophobic forces are not considered. This was done to preserve model tractability and focus on process-level behavior rather than detailed molecular self-assembly mechanisms.

Figure 5. Schematic diagram of electrostatic force in the context of DNA-lipid encapsulation.

2.5.3. Brownian Motion of Particles and Collision Kinetics

Collisions between two particles can be of the following types: lipid–lipid, dna–dna, dna–lipid, capsule–dna, and capsule–lipid. For elastic collisions (first two types in which the particles separate after collision), momentum and kinetic energy are conserved.

With respect to the relative masses, the mass of the DNA and capsule (partially or fully formed) is considered much greater than the mass of the individual lipid. Hence, the DNA or capsule will only have a minimal perturbation in trajectory whereas the lipid perturbation will be more significant. For respective weights, a DNA of 52 base pairs is considered to have a MW of approx. 17,000 g/mol, and each lipid has a MW of 766 g/mol. Hence, a complete capsule (which we consider as three DNA with 15 lipids) will have a weight of $(17,000 \times 3) + (766 \times 15) = 62,490$ g/mol.

Note that the simulated EE% is sensitive to the definition of a ‘completed capsule’ since this rule determines which assemblies are counted as encapsulated structures. A less restrictive criterion, such as two DNA and 10 lipids, would likely increase the absolute EE% values. It is important, however, to distinguish between the physical process and the simulation. In the real system, encapsulation arises from a continuous self-assembly process and is not defined by a single discrete threshold. In the model, by contrast, a fixed rule is necessary to classify structures and compute EE%. The three DNA/15 lipid threshold was adopted because the simulation was originally defined and calibrated around a 1:6 ratio, where good agreement was obtained. The interface nonetheless allows other combinations to be explored through sliders ranging from 1 to 20 lipids and 1–10 DNA.

The collision kinetics also take into account the electrostatic attraction/repulsion and number of lipids already attached to a DNA, as described previously in Section 2.5.2. Figure 6 shows an example of a capsule in formation (Figure 6a) and a completed capsule with three DNAs and 15 lipids (Figure 6b). DNAs and lipids are governed by a weighted probabilistic attraction/repulsion.

In the digital twin simulation, the Brownian motion of particles is implemented by random encounters between particles with kinetic energy considering relative velocity and equal mass for all particles. With reference to Figure 7, in the case of the particles striking the walls of the micromixer, which may be convex, concave or straight, a symmetrical angle

of incidence/exit is considered in all cases, following the laws of reflectance for perfectly circular segment surfaces (that is, non-parabolic, etc.).

Figure 6. Schematic diagram of different scenarios of random kinetic collisions between particles (a,b).

Figure 7. Schematic diagram of collision scenarios of particles with micromixer walls (a–c).

2.5.4. Turbulence Control

Turbulence is to be avoided in the micromixer and is controlled by the Reynolds and Dean values, calculated as follows:

$$Re = \frac{Uh}{\nu}, \quad (1)$$

$$De = Re \times \sqrt{\frac{h}{2R}}, \quad (2)$$

where h is the channel height, ν is the kinematic viscosity of water, and R is the curvature radius of the tori.

Following the indications of [26], the acceptable range for the Reynolds value was defined as between 10 and 1100 and the acceptable range for Dean numbers was defined as between 4 and 400, in order to be outside the risk regions for turbulence development.

2.5.5. Key Performance Indicators—Capsule Size and Encapsulation Efficiency

The capsule size is represented by two values, the average diameter and the *PDI* (poly dispersion index), where the latter is represented in the simulation by the formula

$$PDI = \left(\frac{\sigma}{\mu} \right)^2, \quad (3)$$

where σ is the standard deviation of the diameter and μ is the mean value.

The encapsulation efficiency is estimated in the physical process and the simulation by the formula

$$EE\% = \left(\frac{\text{number of DNA encapsulated}}{\text{total number of DNA}} \right) \times 100. \quad (4)$$

A DNA is considered encapsulated when a capsule is formed which consists of exactly three DNA and 15 lipids.

3. Results

The results are organized into two main parts; firstly, the experimental development of the simulation is given in Section 3.1, followed by details of the resulting simulation and its benchmarking in Section 3.2.

3.1. Micromixer Experiments and Experimental Development of the Simulation

In the following, the details of the digital twin simulation of the physical process (micromixer DNA encapsulation) (Section 3.1.1) and data-driven development of the simulation (Section 3.1.2), are provided.

3.1.1. Digital Twin Simulation of the Physical Process (Micromixer DNA Encapsulation)

As a first step, advanced data analytics (both machine learning and statistical techniques) were applied to establish relations between the input control parameters (FRR, TFR) and the output KPIs (mean diameter, PDI and %EE). It was found that there was no linear relation between the inputs (FRR, TFR) and the outputs, hence non-linear techniques were considered for modeling the data (described in Section 3.1.2).

With respect to TFR (total flow rate), in general, the faster the flow, the smaller the diameter as the DNA and lipids will have less opportunity to interact. For FRR (flow rate ratio), there is an optimum ratio of DNAs to lipids in order to obtain a given (average) diameter and average number of lipids attached to DNAs at the end of the process.

Table 1 shows the set of control parameters for the real process experiments, which was used as a basis for calibrating the simulation, in which Q1 represents the flow of DNA and Q2 the lipids. The N/P ratio was assigned as a constant value of 5.5, as detailed in the reference paper [26]. Experiments two and four have the greatest flow of DNA, whereas experiment three has a greater flow of lipids than DNA. With reference to Table 1, experiment 1 had a Q1 = 3.873 and Q2 = 0.861, giving a FRR of Q1/Q2 = 3.873/0.861 = 4.5, and a TFR of Q1 + Q2 = 3.873 + 0.861 = 4.734.

Table 1. Set of experiments with different FRR (flow rate ratio) and TFR (total flow rate) combinations and corresponding Q1 and Q2 values.

Experiment	FRR (Q1/Q2)	TFR (Q1 + Q2)	Q1 (DNA)	Q2 (Lipids)
1	4.5	4.734	3.873	0.861
2	4.5	11.266	9.218	2.048
3	0.4175	8	2.356	5.644
4	8.5825	8	7.165	0.835
5	4.5	8	6.545	1.455

Note that in the range of flow rates tested for the physical process, the Reynolds and Dean numbers were well below the risk regions for turbulence development. For example, for FRR = 4.5 and TFR = 4.734 the Reynolds number was 526 and the Dean number was 263. This is well below the risk regions for turbulence development. The values in the simulation were also well within these ranges.

3.1.2. Data-Driven Development of the Simulation

In this section, the data-driven aspects are described. From the real empirical data, the system is calibrated: for a set of quantifiable control inputs, it will produce the same, or as similar as possible, quantifiable outputs (key performance indicators) as the physical process.

Inputs: TFR (total flow rate), FRR (flow rate ratio).

Outputs: KPIs for each experiment run: mean capsule diameter, PDI, %EE.

With reference to Table 2, the input combinations of FRR and TFR are the principal variable control parameters of the system. Highlights: (i) Experiments one and two produced a high %EE (over 99%) and close to optimum diameter (average of 65 and 64, respectively). (ii) Experiment five had a high %EE (average over 99%) but the average diameter was somewhat higher than optimum (average 75). (iii) Experiment three (with a very low FRR) produced a significantly lower %EE (62% average) and higher mean diameter (average 89). (iv) Experiment four had a close to optimum average diameter (average 64) but a slightly lower %EE (96% average). In terms of the PDI (poly dispersion index), experiment three gave the lowest value (avg. 0.107), followed by experiment four (0.124), five (0.159), one (0.172), and finally, experiment two gave the highest value.

Table 2. Real process experiments: settings and results (KPIs).

Experiment	FRR	TFR	Diameter Mean	PDI	%EE
1.1	4.5	4.734	62.85	0.150	99.53
1.2	4.5	4.734	66.36	0.170	99.46
1.3	4.5	4.734	64.56	0.174	99.53
1.4	4.5	4.734	62.83	0.222	99.57
1.5	4.5	4.734	62.67	0.142	99.50
2.1	4.5	11.266	64.43	0.204	99.44
2.2	4.5	11.266	65.35	0.171	99.48
2.3	4.5	11.266	67.36	0.199	99.49
2.4	4.5	11.266	62.93	0.176	99.50
2.5	4.5	11.266	61.25	0.169	99.46
3.1	0.4175	8	90.35	0.111	75.17
3.2	0.4175	8	89.87	0.107	47.79
3.3	0.4175	8	90.12	0.128	63.04
3.4	0.4175	8	85.63	0.083	49.74
3.5	0.4175	8	93.38	0.108	73.81
4.1	8.5825	8	69.05	0.214	95.90
4.2	8.5825	8	61.49	0.118	98.37
4.3	8.5825	8	66.02	0.103	98.88
4.4	8.5825	8	61.00	0.047	95.27
4.5	8.5825	8	64.16	0.137	95.39
5.1	4.5	8	68.96	0.153	98.4
5.2	4.5	8	69.88	0.158	99.41
5.3	4.5	8	73.61	0.154	99.54
5.4	4.5	8	79.71	0.143	99.38
5.5	4.5	8	84.92	0.188	99.30

Initial statistical analysis and tools applied included: visualization, correlations, covariances, principal components, multi-variate regression models, clustering and decision tree modeling.

The following describes the clustering and decision tree analysis, which helped to calibrate the simulation and identify decision rules and thresholds (see decision tree).

Figure 8 shows that K-means clustered the data into five clusters, and from Table 2, which is summarized for each combination, the assignment of experiments to clusters

shows that experiments two, four, and part of one are grouped together (cluster 0), parts of experiments five, one and two are grouped together (cluster 3), experiments 5.4 and 5.5 form their own group (cluster 4), as well as experiments 3.1, 3.3, and 3.5 (cluster 1) and 3.2 and 3.4 (cluster 2). Hence, a complex relation is identified between the control inputs and the outputs (KPIs).

Figure 8. K-means clustering and PCA. The x and y axes are the two highest ranked principal components and the labels indicate the corresponding experiment (see Table 2). Note there are five runs for each FRR and TFR combination. Color legend corresponds to cluster ID.

Table 3 shows the cross-correlation matrix of inputs and outputs, and Table 4 shows the principal components generated from the data and used to plot Figure 8. From Table 3, it can be seen that the strongest correlations (0.7 or higher) occur between FRR, mean diameter and %EE, and mean diameter with %EE.

Table 3. Correlation matrix (full dataset).

	FRR	TFR	Mean Diameter	PDI	%EE
FRR	1				
TFR	0	1			
Mean diameter	−0.76	−0.05	1		
PDI	0.12	0.09	−0.27	1	
%EE	0.70	0	−0.76	0.53	1

Values rounded to two decimal places.

Table 4. Top three principal components for experimental results.

Eigenvalue	Proportion	Cumulative	Attribute Components
1.86246	0.46562	0.46562	−0.684Mean_Diam + 0.652FRR + 0.319PDI + 0.072TFR
1.04851	0.26213	0.72774	0.839TFR + 0.484PDI − 0.231FRR + 0.094Mean_Diam
0.86922	0.2173	0.94505	0.803PDI − 0.539TFR − 0.238FRR + 0.091Mean_Diam

Figure 9 shows the result of applying a decision tree algorithm to the clustering (of Figure 8). The decision tree model represents the best of five runs (of the algorithm) which obtained a classification precision of 100%. The decision tree serves to explain the clustering, as each leaf node (e.g., class = 0, red color) corresponds to a cluster ID and the decision path from the top node down to the leaf explains the partition criteria of the cluster. For

example, for the red-/green-colored decision path: IF Mean_Diam NOT \leq 68.12 AND EE \leq 86.555 AND PDI NOT \leq 0.108 THEN class (cluster) = 1 (experiments 3.1, 3.3, 3.5). The decision tree uses a powerful information theory algorithm [30] to choose the optimum variables and numerical thresholds and ranges. Then, we can use these variables and ranges to help control the simulation model in terms of the input control parameters.

Figure 9. Decision tree trained using cluster ID from Figure 8.

3.2. Simulation System Deployment and Benchmarking

The following figures show captures of the user front-end screen of the digital twin developed by the authors, with the control panel (Figure 10), micromixer visualization (Figure 11) and runtime statistics (Figure 12).

Figure 10 shows the simulation software control panel. On the left, the basic and “advanced controls 1” sections and turbulence measures; on the right, the KPI statistics and “advanced controls 2” sections. The basic controls, as described previously, are the flow rate ratio (FRR) and total flow rate (TFR) assigned by “pull down lists”. The advanced controls (1) use “sliders” to define: scale up number of particles, maximum simulation time, % frequency random Brownian movement, maximum displacement Brownian movement, probability of particle interaction and distance for interaction between particles. The turbulence measures display is updated dynamically during the simulation, including the Reynolds and Dean numbers (as described in Section 2.5.4). On the right of Figure 10, the KPI statistics are shown: % particles encapsulated, mean diameter and % of capsules with a diameter between 60 and 90 nm. Also shown is the “advanced control 2” section, with the control “sliders” which define the number of DNAs and lipids to form a capsule, set by default to three and 15, respectively.

Figure 11 shows screenshots of the simulation software main screen with the micromixer visualization at different stages of the process: from top to bottom (i) initial stage, (ii) and (iii) middle stages, (iv) final stage. Particles (DNA, lipids, capsules) flow from left to right. Lipids (green) and DNA (blue) enter from the left channels and are progressively

transformed into yellow particles (partially formed capsules) and red ones (completed capsules). Note that the depiction shown in Figure 11 is not just a simple display, it is the to-scale micromixer simulation itself represented in a 2D virtual environment.

Figure 10. Screenshot of the simulation software control panel: **(left)** basic and advanced controls 1, turbulence measures; **(right)** KPI statistics and advanced controls 2.

Figure 12 shows screenshots of the simulation software main screen with the runtime statistics visualizer: from top to bottom (i) during first stages of the process; (ii) during final stages of the process. It is a dynamic plot updated on each iteration which shows the evolution over time (x-axis) of the number of different types of particles (y-axis): DNAs (green), lipids (blue), partially formed capsules (yellow) and completed capsules (red). During the initial stages of the process (i), the number of lipids increases significantly, the number of DNAs remains more constant, the number of partially formed capsules increases progressively, and the number of fully formed capsules remains low. During the final stages of the process (ii), the number of lipids, DNA and partially formed capsules falls significantly, whereas the number of fully formed capsules finally starts to decline having previously been constantly maintained.

Table 5 shows the results for the five FRR/TFR combinations, with five runs of the digital twin simulation for each combination. The resulting KPIs were recorded and are shown in the last three columns of Table 5.

Figure 11. Screenshots of the simulation software main screen with the micromixer visualization at different stages of the process: from top to bottom (i) initial stage, (ii,iii) middle stages, (iv) final stage.

Table 6 shows the RMSEP fit between the real data (Table 2) and the simulated data (Table 5). It can be seen that there is a close fit of the simulated data with respect to the real data, with the RMSEP ranging from 1.4 to 4.0 for average diameter, from 0.01 to 0.05 for PDI and from 0.3 to 6.5 for EE. To interpret this margin of error, the average value for each KPI for the real data can be compared with the error margin. For average diameter, the real average diameter for all experiments is 71.55, for PDI the average value is 0.15 and for %EE,

the average value is 91.37. It can be seen that experiments three and five had a relatively worse fit, and experiments one, two and four had a relatively better fit. This agrees with the real experimental results which were more dispersed for experiments three and five. A closer fitting could be performed, but the tradeoff between the model's generalization ability and overfitting to specific outcomes must also be taken into consideration.

Figure 12. Screenshots of the simulation software main screen with the runtime statistics visualizer: (upper) during first stages of the process; (lower) during final stages of the process.

With reference to Figure 13a–c, for the simulated data, five runs were conducted for each experiment, the same number of runs as the real empirical tests. The real vs simulated fitting values (RMSEP) correspond to those given in Table 6.

Table 5. Data generated by simulation for the same experimental settings (FRR/TFR) as physical process experiments.

Experiment	FRR	TFR	Diameter Mean	PDI	%EE
1.1	4.5	4.734	65.97	0.163	99.84
1.2	4.5	4.734	72.91	0.116	99.94
1.3	4.5	4.734	62.44	0.147	99.63
1.4	4.5	4.734	63.95	0.299	99.33
1.5	4.5	4.734	64.62	0.129	99.72
2.1	4.5	11.266	62.01	0.166	98.44
2.2	4.5	11.266	63.11	0.159	97.81
2.3	4.5	11.266	67.63	0.187	99.59
2.4	4.5	11.266	64.09	0.152	98.13
2.5	4.5	11.266	69.61	0.191	97.10
3.1	0.4175	8	91.39	0.124	78.66
3.2	0.4175	8	88.67	0.138	64.15
3.3	0.4175	8	77.86	0.12	59.55
3.4	0.4175	8	86.95	0.127	63.17
3.5	0.4175	8	89.51	0.093	44.46
4.1	8.5825	8	62.71	0.191	93.21
4.2	8.5825	8	67.41	0.064	98.32
4.3	8.5825	8	61.47	0.125	97.22
4.4	8.5825	8	58.74	0.165	91.12
4.5	8.5825	8	68.37	0.128	95.80
5.1	4.5	8	76.71	0.101	98.93
5.2	4.5	8	69.37	0.067	97.29
5.3	4.5	8	76.62	0.23	98.44
5.4	4.5	8	75.24	0.21	97.70
5.5	4.5	8	71.35	0.153	96.98

Table 6. RMSEP * fit between real data (Table 2) and simulated data (Table 5).

Experiment	FRR	TFR	Average Diameter	PDI	%EE
1	4.5	4.734	3.1	0.04	0.3
2	4.5	11.266	1.5	0.01	1.5
3	0.4175	8	3.9	0.01	6.5
4	8.5825	8	1.4	0.02	2.2
5	4.5	8	4.0	0.05	1.4

* Root mean square error of prediction.

Figure 13. Cont.

Figure 13. (a) Continuous plot of capsule diameter, real vs simulated, for experiments one to five (a straight diagonal line from the lower left to upper right would be a perfect correlation). (b) Continuous plot of poly dispersion index, real vs simulated, for experiments one to five (a straight diagonal line from the lower left to upper right would be a perfect correlation). (c) Continuous plot of encapsulation efficiency, real vs simulated, for experiments one to five (a straight diagonal line from the lower left to upper right would be a perfect correlation).

From Figure 13a, it can be seen that runs three and five were the most similar in distribution and runs one, two and four had the closest diameter values. In Figure 13b, it can be seen that the PDI numerical values for runs two, three and four have the closest correlation (real vs simulation). Figure 13c shows a somewhat different trend for the %EE, in which experiment three has a wider distribution on the lower segment of the diagonal, experiments one, two and five are very close together in the upper right diagonal, and experiment four is slightly lower down on the diagonal.

4. Discussion

It was found that the system behavior in the physical process and the simulation agreed with the key previous empirical study of reference [26], in which FRR was the key factor affecting mixing and LNP size, with an optimum value target of 60 nm and size greater than 100 nm considered unviable. While there is a tendency in industrial digital twin literature to focus on industrial production deployment [31–33], we have shown that support tools to enhance laboratory-scale experiments are also a key application area. Furthermore, although industrial digital twin software such as DynoChem V4.1 [34] and Matlab Simulink R2026a [35], among others, are undeniably adequate for many applications, they are based on deterministic programming, theoretical definitions and a ‘top down’ approach. Multi-agent systems, with their stochastic and emergent behavior and ‘bottom-up’ approach, provide a contrast with and serve as a consensus benchmark versus more traditional approaches.

In the present case, the end user (Reig Jofre Laboratories) was interested in obtaining a tool which can simulate different combinations of control settings for the micromixer. In this way, unviable combinations can be discounted, and more promising ones can be focused on in order to define individual or sets of experiments. This clearly offers the significant advantages of a reduction in time, effort, cost, and use of expensive materials during the execution of laboratory experiments.

For future work, simulation of the scale-up (of the physical process) could be considered, which is a key issue when moving from the laboratory to the industrial environment. Note that the Repast Simphony software development tool is designed for small-, medium-, or large-scale simulations (it was developed at the Argonne National Laboratory, United States, for high energy physics and chemical studies). There is a different version (with process parallelism) for high computation needs, and this also requires adequate hardware for execution. Further, a more explicit definition of the micromixer wall shear stress and resistance formulas could be considered.

5. Conclusions

This paper has detailed the development of an *in silico* simulation of a micromixer encapsulation process, which combines theoretical definitions, data-driven modeling and stochastic/emergent behavior. It shows the viability of developing a simulation for such a process and its utility for supporting researchers working on laboratory-scale experiments. In the context of sustainability, testing *in silico* saves time, resources and cost/effort for physical experiments, and serves as a support tool to help identify the most promising control parameter combinations. With respect to the physical process, the micromixer approach for encapsulation optimizes resources and reduces waste.

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: (demo video) <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ulNT4V4PigcBNb7fQRGpQmq0QvaRFcwY/view?usp=sharing> (accessed on 1 April 2026). (presentation) <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1CsHePhnHZxf9KykF5y-SFWOxrVwwk3NQ/view?usp=sharing> (accessed on 1 April 2026).

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

AI	Artificial Intelligence
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic Acid
EE	Encapsulation Efficiency
ETERNAL	Boosting the reduction of the Environmental impact of pharmaceutical products throughout their entire life cycle
FRR	Flow Rate Ratio
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LNP	Lipid Nanoparticle
MAS	Multi-Agent System
N/P	Nitrogen to Phosphate Ratio
PCA	Principal Components Analysis
PDI	Poly Dispersion Index
PEG	Polyethylene Glycol
TFR	Total Flow Rate

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